

**Cognitive Engineering Computer Interfaces: Part II -
An Objective Design Process**

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Abstract

Much is being written about "cognitive engineering," the process by which psychology and human factors engineering data are applied to human interface design. Most of this literature is strong on theoretic advocacy of such a process but weak on implementation details. The present paper is an attempt to describe a process that will combine 1) knowledge acquisition, 2) human cognitive data, 3) human engineering data, 4) hardware and software constraints, and 5) aesthetics to derive a set of interface specifications whose details can be justified based on objective cognitive engineering criteria. An example based on efforts to assist development of the next generation Command Tactical Information System (CTIS), the command and control system of the Air Force's Alaskan Command, will be presented.

The increasing use of the term "cognitive engineering" in interface design is both encouraging and discouraging. It is encouraging because interface design engineers are finally acknowledging that just displaying information is not sufficient for a successful interface; the system operator must be able to receive and use the information. This fact has been reinforced by such publicized incidents as the crash of the French Airbus outside Strasbourg, France (Sparaco, 1994). In that incident all the necessary information to prevent the accident was available to the crew, but their failure to understand it led to calamity. It would be easy to attribute such an accident to "operator error," since the information was available to the crew. However, there was clear evidence that the information in the two auto pilot modes was easily confused. Blaming the operators would ignore the failure of the display

interfaces to make important descent rate information understandable.

The use of the term "cognitive engineering" is discouraging because neither is it being defined nor is anything being written about how to do it! There are several reasons for these glaring oversights. The first reason is the failure of both psychologists and engineers to understand each other's domains. Psychologists have problems developing applied data that is generalized to broad classes of problems. The engineering process is alien to them, so they do not collect or express the kinds of data the engineering process demands. Engineers, on the other hand, tend to be ignorant of user cognitive processes when presenting information on the screen. Specifications are hard enough to write - Imagine a contract specification that says you must display A, B and C and the operator must understand and react accurately! Verifying such a functional requirement would be difficult; how much understanding is good enough? The whole problem runs contrary to the legalized acquisition process. Invariably, such questions are left up to the operational test and evaluation (OTE) organizations and by then, changes are difficult or impossible to implement.

By no means does this paper claim to completely define how cognitive engineering should be conducted. However, it will attempt to begin by defining *one way* to do cognitive engineering. Webster's dictionary (1977) defines cognition as "the act or process of knowing, including both awareness and judgment." Engineering is defined as "the application of science and mathematics by which the properties of matter and sources of energy in nature are made useful to man in structures, machines, products, systems, and processes." Cognitive engineering would use the properties of the operator's awareness and judgment in the engineering process.

Now that we have a definition, how would someone go about doing cognitive engineering? The proposed cognitive engineering process will consist of a combination of five distinct processes. These steps are 1) knowledge acquisition, 2) consideration of human cognitive performance, 3) consideration of human perceptual and motor performance, 4) hardware and software constraints, and 5) aesthetics (see Figure 1). Hardware and software engineering are the domain of the conventional engineer. Human factors engineering contributes to the engineering process with valuable information about human operator perceptual and motor performance and some information about cognitive processes. Cognitive engineering expands on the importance of cognitive capabilities and adds information from cognitive maps, decision process assessment, and other insights into the operator side of the user interface.

Figure 1: Defining cognitive engineering and explaining its relationship with other aspects of engineering.

Another aspect of cognition in design is the aesthetics of the design; attractive designs are more readily accepted by users. Even given the boundary conditions from the other five stages, there is considerable latitude in the final form of a design. Appreciation of artistic attractiveness is a cognitive process whose importance in design acceptance cannot be ignored. Merely suggesting aesthetics are important in engineering is a radical idea. This paper will not consider aesthetics, leaving it for later consideration.

The first step of cognitive engineering, knowledge acquisition, is a practical spin-off from artificial intelligence research. Developers of expert systems have produced elaborate strategies for learning and organizing the information on which the expert system is based. Armstrong Laboratory researchers (McFarren, M. R., 1987; Gomes, M.E., Lind, S. and

Snyder, D.E., 1992; Zaff, B.S., McNeese, M.D. & Snyder, D.E., 1993) and others have recognized that concept mapping-based knowledge acquisition could be extremely valuable to design engineers. Both the content and organization of operator knowledge needs to be considered in the form and function of the interface.

Most often knowledge acquisition is accomplished by observation and by interview. These can be quite effective, but more standardized and rigorous methods are required. The local approach has been to use a process called concept mapping (Novak, J. D. & Gowin, D.B., 1984) to capture the knowledge and organize it. A content analysis of the concept map is used to extract the essence of information from the map to reveal important trends within and between maps. Specialized software is under development to somewhat automate the creation and analysis of concept maps. This process is described by Lind and Marshak (1994) with an example data taken from the Alaskan Rescue Coordination Center (RCC) staff at Elmendorf Air Force Base, AK and include observations made during actual rescue operations (Doto, 1993).

Several salient features in the concept map are derived from the RCC staff. First, a major responsibility which plays some part in all aspects of the mission is maintenance of the log. A permanent record of all input information and all output actions must be maintained and is tracked by chronology and by incident number. It is clear that many other screen entries are also relevant to the log as well, which suggests the log should automatically receive that information. Ready access to the log should be a salient feature of the user interface.

A second discovery during observations and interviews was the heavy reliance on paper navigational maps in organizing and conducting the search. Maps of various scales are used and multiple scales may be necessary simultaneously. Frequent inputs are received from Search And Rescue Satellites (SARSAT) over a linkage to National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Agency's (NOAA) control center regarding reports of electronic locator transmitters (ELTs) signals received during satellite passes. These ELTs can originate from downed aircraft, lost individuals equipped with personal ELTs or false alarms (caused by hard aircraft landings or mimicking radiation). Currently operators must hand plot ELT signals and correlate them with reports of overdue aircraft or missing persons. The

current computer system (the Digital Decision Display System [3DS] which is a component of CTIS) has a digitized map capability tied to radar tracking, but it is not designed to handle RCC mission planning. Clearly, a versatile map management system would significantly enhance RCC mission planning.

The impact of knowledge acquisition can be seen in comparing the proposed structure for the RCC software (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Complex hierarchical screen structure being used in RCC software.

Each block represents a screen, the particulars of which are not immediately important. This structure has up to four layers and must be traversed by a layered menu system much like the current RCC software system based on text screens. Log and remark functions are located in four locations, and many other functions involve log events.

The proposed alternative form (see Figure 3) uses a single layer organization, with a central menu supplemented by "hot key" shifts directly from screen to screen. A common operator complaint with menu driven systems is the difficulty of getting from screen A to screen B. A central menu available from all screens permits inexperienced users to "pick" the screen (pick in the graphical user interface sense) they wish to use. The hot keys allow experienced operators to move quickly between screens without their hands even leaving the keyboard home keys. Auto linking between related screens would be accomplished where mandatory inputs are required. Log maintenance would be part of every screen, allowing operators to make manual inputs or monitor automatic log entries.

Figure 3: Proposed alternative screen structure for use in the RCC software

The second stage of cognitive engineering of the RCC display system must draw upon existing human engineering data to determine the content of each display. Some aspects of the displays and controls are well understood and easily specified. Typical of the decisions that can be based on human performance is screen size, whether or not to use color coding, whether to make color redundant with other coding or a sole basis for discrimination (eliminating color blind operators), and how many or which colors to use. Another decision is the size and font used for text, which is also dependent on screen size and other terminal capabilities. Decisions can be based on databases of human performance such as Boff and Lincoln (1988). Most engineering disciplines offer very specific guidelines about how to engineer a particular kind of item. Various organizations offer a number of such human factors guidelines (Military Standard 1472-D, NASA Standard 3000, etc.). These guidelines are usually application specific (such as aircraft cockpits or space systems) and may or may not readily be generalized to other settings. Most of these standards are based on human perceptual or motor limitations and do not include cognitive capabilities.

Unfortunately, there is no such standards for the cognitive performance by operators. On some high-cost, high-impact systems, engineering interfaces are usually an iterative process done through mock-up, part-task or full-task simulations. They literally try designs and judge their relative effectiveness by objective or subjective evaluations. Although

simulation is most effective, it is still prone to the influence of fidelity-based artifacts so simulation does not guarantee success. A less expensive (and less effective) alternative practice is rapid prototyping of displays and controls. Such prototyping usually uses computer software to visualize the interface, sometimes giving the interface rudimentary functionality. Operators can at least see a facsimile of the final displays and controls and do subjective evaluations. Alaskan Command is using graphics software to prototype their new screens. These interface prototypes are shown to users for subjective evaluation and comment.

On most low-cost systems (and even some high-cost ones), design is left to the judgment of hardware and software engineers with the advice of operators and a human factors "staff." The hardware and software engineers have little or no training to predict the effectiveness of their design, time pressures lead them to fast solutions and their limited experience with the overall operation of the system give them a poor basis for design decisions. The bottom line is that operators are sometimes left to make the best of whatever interface is provided.

The knowledge acquisition process and human engineering data can go a long way to help specify the cognitive aspects of the system interface. Designers who know what operators will do and how they do it will produce a better product than those who do not have the knowledge. An example of this in the RCC is the central role of the logging of events in a search. Every input and every action is recorded in a daily log which is tracked by time and by particular rescue. Careful examination of the map specifies the kinds of information the log should receive. The plans call out a separate log screen that would be menu selected. The concept map advocates automatic update of the log from input and actions as well as the ability to make manual entries from anyplace in the rescue process. This suggests a separate tiled window (rather than overlapped window) constantly available for input and automatic update of the log from other functions.

The third stage of the cognitive engineering process is to resolve hardware and software constraints with which the system must operate. Typical hardware constraints might be screen size and resolution, colors available, graphics processor power, update rates, and input/output devices. The engineers are painfully aware of these limitations and the designers also need to understand them. Designers in the second stage need

to remain constantly aware of these constraints and ensure they are not specifying things that cannot be easily accomplished without justification. If the displays and controls are computer based, then software constraints will exist as well. Choice of hardware limits the choice of software suited to that system. Choice of a computer operating system and interface software make development easier but in doing so determines many of the features of the user interface.

Alaskan Command's software development team has chosen the Open Software Foundation version of the Unix operating system (also satisfying the military POSIX standard) and the Motif user interface (Berlage, 1991) running on top of the X-Windows user interface library. The Motif implementation uses standardized software "widgets" for buttons, sliders, windows, and other implementation details. Thus, the software functionality of the RCC interface will be highly portable between UNIX systems but must use these standardized parts for compatibility. The cognitive engineering process must utilize these components in the interface. This is not a severe constraint, because the Motif library of features is quite rich, but it is a constraint none the less.

Even after knowledge acquisition, human performance data, hardware and software constraints, considerable latitude is left in specifying the form of user interface. Exhausting the scientific specification of the interface, the designer is left to determine the final form by art. This is really no different from how hardware engineers operate. After all function is determined, the final appearance of a product is often left to the artist. Many industrial designers have art training, and designers like Gucci flaunt the beauty as well as functionality of their products. User acceptance is based on more than functionality, and it is very short sighted to believe otherwise. The RCC interface must use functional and pleasing fonts, colors, and arrangements to win user acceptance.

Consider one possible screen for use in the Alaskan Command RCC (see Figure 4). Cognitively engineered features of this screen include 1) flatter menu structure to reach all functions, 2) tiled windows including a permanent window for log entries, 3) font sizes and color combinations based on human perception standards, 4) broader use of digitized maps to replace paper maps, 5) use of Motif widgets for making inputs and 6) alternative pointing devices for

interaction with maps (including mice, tablets and light pens).

The proposed schema for cognitive engineering is only a first approximation at defining how to proceed. There is no doubt that alternative explanations are possible which may better define the process. Certainly, further detail of how to proceed at each step can be added. It is hoped that the process and its example will trigger more and better thinking about what cognitive engineering is and how it should be conducted.

Figure 4: Generic screen design based on cognitive engineering.

Notes

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